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Psycho-Yogic Interventions and Eating Attitudes: Cultural Relevance and Efficacy in Indian Young Adults

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Abstract

This study investigates the impact of psycho-yogic interventions—integrating mindfulness, yoga, and counseling—on eating attitudes among young adults in India, a population increasingly at risk for eating disorders due to cultural and societal pressures. Utilizing chi-square analyses, the research assesses the effectiveness of psycho-yogic practices in modifying disordered eating attitudes, as measured by the Eating Attitudes Test (EAT-26). Results reveal a significant improvement in eating attitudes within the intervention group, underscoring the cultural relevance and therapeutic value of psycho-yogic practices for Indian youth. This study contributes to the literature on culturally aligned interventions, suggesting that mindfulness-based practices are both acceptable and effective in addressing disordered eating behaviors in young adults.

Keywords:

Psycho-yogic interventions, eating attitudes, young adults, India, mindfulness, cultural relevance

1. Introduction

Eating disorders, such as anorexia nervosa, bulimia nervosa, and binge eating disorder, present significant health risks, often originating in adolescence and early adulthood. The National Eating Disorders Association (2022) has highlighted the increasing prevalence of these conditions, underscoring the need for effective interventions. In India, the rapid influence of Western ideals of thinness and societal pressures has led to rising body dissatisfaction among young adults, increasing the susceptibility to disordered eating behaviors (Sharma & Coutinho, 2016).

Despite traditional therapeutic models like cognitive-behavioral therapy (CBT) being effective in modifying maladaptive behaviors, their application may lack cultural sensitivity for Indian populations. Psycho-yogic interventions, which integrate mindfulness and yoga with psychological counseling, present a promising, culturally resonant approach to address disordered eating. Yoga and mindfulness are historically rooted in Indian culture, emphasizing holistic wellness, self-regulation, and body awareness (Khalsa et al., 2015). This study examines the efficacy of psycho-yogic interventions on eating attitudes in Indian young adults, exploring the cultural relevance of these practices as tools for improving mental health outcomes.

2. Literature Review

The cultural foundation of mindfulness and yoga in India lends these practices unique therapeutic potential, particularly for addressing body image concerns and reducing anxiety. Research has demonstrated that yoga enhances physical and emotional awareness, while mindfulness fosters a non-judgmental approach to self-perception, which is beneficial for individuals with disordered eating behaviors (Brown & Ryan, 2003; Sahni et al., 2015). However, most studies have focused on the independent effects of mindfulness or yoga, with limited exploration of their combined impact as psycho-yogic interventions.

Studies conducted within Indian contexts have observed positive outcomes in body image and emotional regulation among young adults practicing yoga, supporting its cultural acceptability and relevance (Singh & Goyal, 2020). Furthermore, psycho-yogic approaches address multiple dimensions of disordered eating by improving self-acceptance, reducing anxiety, and fostering a positive relationship with one's body (Culbert et al., 2015). By incorporating traditional practices into a structured intervention, this study seeks to contribute to the limited literature on culturally aligned approaches for young adults in India at risk for eating disorders.

Research indicates that dietary attitudes and behaviours varies markedly among many ethnic groups, including those in India. Research indicates that Indian individuals had eating behaviours comparable to or more detrimental than those of Western countries, despite a lesser desire for thinness (Kayano et al., 2008). The correlation between body mass index and eating attitudes among Indian individuals varied from that seen in Western groups (Kayano et al., 2008).

Cultural variables significantly influence dietary attitudes and behaviours. In India, yoga, with its profound cultural heritage, has been recognised as a viable intervention for enhancing health and well-being in elderly persons (Muralidhar et al., 2023). Cultural constraints, like ageism and gender role expectations, might impede the adoption of these approaches, especially for women (Muralidhar et al., 2023). Considering these cultural differences, investigating psycho-yogic therapies for eating attitudes in young Indian people is pertinent and possibly significant.

This study issue tackles a significant gap in comprehending the interplay of cultural practices, psychological therapies, and eating attitudes within the Indian environment. By concentrating on young adults, it addresses a vital population when dietary behaviours and perceptions are frequently established, potentially influencing long-term health outcomes (Ashton et al., 2019; Sivasubramanian, 2024). The cultural significance of yoga in India, along with the necessity for focused therapies to tackle eating behaviours, renders this study issue very relevant and intriguing.

Culture affects eating disorders because body weight, shape, and thinness are viewed differently. Eating habits in non-Western societies have been studied little. Since societal norms, cultural values, and media portrayals impact body image differently internationally, this gap must be bridged. Comparing Japanese, Indian, Omani, Filipino, and Euro-American teens' body weight and disordered eating habits indicates cultural similarities and differences.

Cultural and media promotion of thinness can lead to body dissatisfaction and fat phobia, making eating disorders frequent in Western countries (Keel & Klump, 2003). Recent study suggests that globalisation and Westernisation of beauty ideals are increasing disordered eating across Asia and the Middle East (Nasser et al., 2001). Japanese women value thinness, but a new study reveals that men are equally encouraged to be slender (Ozawa et al., 2010). Japanese thinness preoccupation is linked to body dissatisfaction and limited eating, like Western countries.

Teens in India, Oman, and the Philippines eat differently. These people ate similarly or worse than Western and Japanese people, but they craved less thinness. Thus, disordered eating is frequent but may have several reasons. Unlike Western norms that associate thinness with attractiveness and success, non-Western nations may view body size via health, family traditions, or social standing (Mumford et al., 1991). In some Indian and Filipino communities, weight is associated to income and health, not beauty, confusing thinness and obsessive eating.

In addition, BMI and eating habits or fat phobia vary greatly among Western and Japanese Indian, Omani, and Filipino groups. This highlights how complex body image and eating behaviours are in non-Western cultures, where body dissatisfaction may not correspond with body size. Fast globalisation and Western media exposure have transformed these nations' thinness values, producing disordered eating (Furnham & Alibhai, 1983).

In Indian, Omani, and Filipino populations, both men and women had bad eating habits, unlike Western research where women mostly have eating disorders. Muscle and leanness are increasingly influencing non-Western male body image standards (Griffiths et al., 2016).

Sociocultural variables affect body image and eating habits across ethnic groups, showing that body size and eating attitudes differ. Fat phobia and thinness disparities require culturally customised eating disorder treatments worldwide. Thinness-related eating disorders were seen in Western and Japanese teens, but cultural, societal, and family factors affected Indian, Omani, and Filipino teens.

In conclusion, sociocultural influences influence each ethnic group's attitudes and disordered eating. The study's comparative approach underlines the need for culturally appropriate tools to evaluate and treat eating disorders globally, as causes and symptoms vary by nation. Comprehensive eating disorder understanding and effective treatments for diverse communities require this cross-cultural perspective.

3. Methodology

Image:1 Description of Variables

3.1 Participants

This study recruited 100 young adults (aged 19-30) from Indian universities, split equally into experimental (n=50) and control (n=50) groups. Ethical approval was obtained, and all participants provided informed consent. Inclusion criteria required participants to score above the threshold on the EAT-26, indicating a predisposition to disordered eating behaviors.

3.2 Research Design

Image:2 Presentation of groups

3.3 Intervention Design

To treat disordered eating in young people, the intervention strategy uses Surya Namaskar, Pranakarshan Pranayam, mindfulness meditation, and CBT. The 12-week Intervention program (60-minute group sessions) for daily basis. A dynamic 12-posture yoga sequence called Surya Namaskar starts each session to improve body awareness, strength, and mental calm. Next is Pranakarshan Pranayam, a concentrated breathing exercise to regulate energy flow, relieve tension, and relax the mind. Mindfulness meditation promotes emotional control and self-acceptance by increasing awareness and decreasing judgement. The third component uses CBT to change

eating-related negative thoughts, beliefs, and behaviours. This comprehensive method promotes healthy food and body image connections and self-regulation and emotional well-being by tackling physical and cognitive-emotional elements.

Image:3 Application procedure of psycho-yogic Intervention

1. Sun Salutation/ Surya Namaskar

Surya Namaskar is a flowing sequence of 12 yoga postures done in the morning on an empty stomach. It boosts metabolism, cardiovascular health, muscular tone, and mental wellbeing. This technique improves bodily awareness and mental calm, helping participants create healthy body interactions.

2. Pranakarshan Prananyam

By managing prana (vital energy), this breathing exercise balances energy channels (nadis). Prana absorption and release through conscious breath and deliberate, intentional expiration improve energy flow, tension, and tranquilly. Sessions last 15 minutes and include 5 cycles.

3. Meditating Mindfully

Mindfulness meditation, adopted from Buddhist practice, emphasises nonjudgmental observation of thoughts, feelings, and body sensations. It promotes acceptance, calm, and clarity. Jon Kabat-Zinn's Mindfulness-Based Stress Reduction (MBSR) popularised this technique, which helps regulate emotions.

4. Counselling based on Cognitive-Behavioral Therapy

CBT is a goal-oriented, problem-solving approach to change harmful thinking patterns and behaviours. CBT uses practical, hands-on methods to increase emotional well-being by focussing on ideas, beliefs, pictures, and attitudes. This intervention uses CBT, yoga, and mindfulness to address maladaptive cognitive processes, challenging negative beliefs, improving self-awareness, and promoting healthy behaviours.

The physical and cognitive-emotional elements of disordered eating behaviours are addressed in this holistic approach to improve food, body image, and self-regulation.

3.4 Measures

Eating attitudes were assessed using the EAT-26, a validated tool for identifying disordered eating patterns. BMI data were also collected pre- and post-intervention, though not central to this study's primary focus on eating attitudes. The chi-square test was used to evaluate the association between the psycho-yogic intervention and changes in EAT-26 scores.

3.5 Hypothesis (H0) There is no significant effect of Psycho-yogic intervention on Eating attitude in Young adults at the risk of eating disorder in Experimental and Controlled group participants towards Pre-test and Post-test score values on EAT-26.

3.6 Data Analysis

Chi-square tests assessed within- and between-group changes in EAT-26 scores and BMI outcomes. Significance was set at $p < .05$.

4. Results

4.1 Chi-Square Test Results

The chi-square test results for eating attitudes (EAT-26 scores) in the post-test analysis indicated a significant association between the psycho-yogic intervention and improved scores in the intervention group:

Chi-Square Test	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	14.156	2	.001
Likelihood Ratio	15.929	2	.000
Linear-by-Linear Association	13.816	1	.000
N of Valid Cases	100		

These results confirm a statistically significant improvement in eating attitudes within the intervention group. The minimum expected count was 7.50, with 0% of cells having counts below five, validating the reliability of the test outcomes.

4.2 BMI Outcomes

BMI analysis yielded no significant association with the intervention, as indicated by the chi-square results (Pearson Chi-Square = 1.251, $df = 2$, $p = .535$). This suggests that while psycho-yogic practices influence cognitive and emotional aspects of disordered eating, they do not produce immediate physiological changes such as BMI reduction over a 12-week period.

5. Discussion

The findings support the hypothesis that psycho-yogic interventions can significantly improve eating attitudes among young adults at risk for eating disorders in India, although they do not directly affect BMI outcomes. The significant post-test improvement in EAT-26 scores within the intervention group suggests that psycho-yogic practices enhance body awareness, emotional regulation, and self-acceptance, aligning with previous research on the psychological benefits of yoga and mindfulness (Brown & Ryan, 2003; Sahni et al., 2015).

The lack of effect on BMI suggests that physical changes may require additional interventions, such as nutritional counseling or increased physical activity, to complement psycho-yogic practices. However, the observed improvements in eating attitudes underscore the potential of psycho-yogic interventions to address the emotional and cognitive dimensions of disordered eating, which are essential to fostering long-term behavioral change.

Cultural Relevance

The integration of mindfulness and yoga, deeply rooted in Indian culture, likely contributed to the intervention's acceptability and efficacy. This cultural alignment may enhance adherence and engagement, as young adults in India are familiar with and open to these practices. Psycho-yogic interventions thus present a valuable, culturally tailored option for mental health practitioners in India, particularly for youth populations facing modern societal pressures around body image.

6. Conclusion

This study demonstrates that psycho-yogic interventions significantly improve eating attitudes among Indian young adults at risk for eating disorders. The cultural resonance of yoga and mindfulness enhances their acceptability, supporting the integration of these practices into preventive mental health strategies within Indian contexts. Future research should explore longer interventions, larger sample sizes, and complementary methods to further investigate the physiological effects of psycho-yogic practices on BMI. Overall, these findings contribute to the growing body of

literature on culturally relevant, holistic approaches for managing disordered eating in young adults.

7. Limitations and Future Directions

The study's limitations include its short duration and the absence of a long-term follow-up to evaluate sustained effects. Future studies could examine the long-term impact of psycho-yogic interventions and include diverse populations to enhance generalizability. Additionally, exploring the specific components of psycho-yogic interventions, such as the role of mindfulness versus yoga postures, may provide insights into refining these practices for greater efficacy.

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